
Understanding pore formation in reactive acrylic thermoplastic resin upon polymerization

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Boosting short-distance rail transport by reopening small railway lines that still exist across the country is possible !

Conventional railway

Steel rails of high CO₂ footprint

Need for an Innovative light railway infrastructure with functionalized composite rails

- ✓ Reducing transport's carbon footprint
- ✓ Digitizing and automating rail transport
- ✓ Cutting costs and facilitate line maintenance

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Porosities in pultruded thick composite rails

- Continuous-fibre recyclable thermoplastic composite rails
- Rails manufacturing by reactive thermoplastic pultrusion

Need for an Innovative light railway infrastructure with functionalized composite rails

- ✓ Reducing transport's carbon footprint
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Impregnation
at P_{atm}

Polymerization
at $P \approx P_{atm}$

- Continuous-fibre recyclable **thermoplastic composite** rails
- Rails manufactured by **reactive thermoplastic pultrusion**

+

Cross-section of a pultruded glass/Elium[®] composite profile

Mechanical source

Capillary forces

vs.

Viscous forces

$$Ca = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma}$$

$$d\vec{F}_\eta = \eta \Delta \vec{v} d\tau$$

Slow Injection flow speed

Fast Injection flow speed

For a specific fluid of known μ and γ
 → Optimal impregnation velocity

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Physico-Chemical formation of porosities

Mechanical source

Capillary forces

vs.

Viscous forces

$$Ca = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma}$$

$$d\vec{F}_\eta = \eta \Delta \vec{v} d\tau$$

Physico-Chemical source

Low M_w
molecules

High vapor
pressure

vs. (Pressure, Temp.)

- Reaction by-products
- Dissolved gases and volatiles
- Moisture

When $P_{matrix} < P_{vapor}$

The bulk pressure is no longer sufficient to solubilize the volatile phase, which is a necessary condition to form pores

Mechanical source

Physico-Chemical source

Capillary forces

vs.

Viscous forces

$$Ca = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma}$$

$$d\vec{F}_\eta = \eta \Delta \vec{v} d\tau$$

Low M_w molecules

High vapor pressure

vs. (Pressure, Temp.)

Pore growth + Coalescence

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(\alpha, T) \\ \gamma(\alpha, T) \\ \rho(\alpha, T) \\ D(\alpha, T) \end{aligned}$$

Spherical void growth model

Coalescence process

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Viscosity

Mechanical source

Capillary forces

vs.

Viscous forces

$$Ca = \frac{\mu v}{\gamma}$$

$$d\vec{F}_\eta = \eta \Delta \vec{v} d\tau$$

ELIUM[®]
ARKEMA

Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA
→ **MMA** has a low Mw (100.12 g.mol⁻¹)

Resin of low viscosity (100cP)

→ Surface tension still under investigation, but mechanical formation of porosities can be controlled by adjusting the impregnation velocity

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Evaporation

The volatile specie is the monomer !

→ $P_{V_{MMA}}(20^{\circ}\text{C}) = 51.3 \text{ hPa}$ at 20°C

→ $T_{\text{boil}} = 101,3^{\circ}\text{C}$ at P_{atm}

Physico-Chemical source

- Reaction by-products
- Dissolved gases and volatiles
- Moisture

Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA
 → **MMA** has a low Mw ($100.12 \text{ g.mol}^{-1}$)

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Evaporation

The volatile specie is the monomer ! And it can boil !

- at low pressure during Outgassing
- upon heating at low temperature ($T_{boil} = 101,3^{\circ}\text{C}$ at P_{atm})

Physico-Chemical source

Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA

→ **MMA** has a low Mw (100.12 g.mol⁻¹)

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Evaporation

MMA Polymerization into PMMA

⇒ ↑ M_w

⇒ ↓ P_{vapour}

⇒ $P_{vapour} < P_{bulk}$ and/or ↑ μ

→ Evaporation stops

ELIUM[®]
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Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA

+

Mixture with 3 Peroxide initiators (3phr)

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Evaporation

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ARKEMA

Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA

+

Mixture with 3 Peroxide initiators (3phr)

Boiling increases MMA evaporation kinetics
→ Pore nucleation is critical

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Boiling

Uncontrolled polymerization of neat Elium[®] resin

Physico-Chemical source

- Reaction by-products
- Dissolved gases and volatiles
- Moisture

ELIUM[®]
ARKEMA

Mixture of **Monomer Methyl-MethAcrylate (MMA)** with PMMA
 → **MMA** has a low Mw (100.12 g.mol⁻¹)

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Boiling

Physico-Chemical source

- Reaction by-products
- Dissolved gases and volatiles
- Moisture

Theory of nucleation based on changes in Gibbs Free Energy

$$G_{liq.}(T, P_{vapor}) = G_{gaz}(T, P_{vapor})$$

$$\text{Nucleation density [m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\text{]} : J = J_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_{homog.}}{k_B T}\right)$$

$$\text{with } \Delta G_{homog.} = \frac{16\pi\gamma}{3(\Delta P)^2}$$

Mechanisms of Porosity formation

Case of Elium[®] acrylic reactive system - Boiling

$$\mu(\alpha, T), \gamma(\alpha, T), \rho(\alpha, T)$$

Physico-Chemical source

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Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Experimental approach by the direct observation of pore growth in a glass tube filled with the acrylic reactive system with application of a hydrostatic pressure

Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Conditions for Porosity in Bulk Resin ?

Experimental approach by the direct observation of pore growth in a glass tube filled with the acrylic reactive system with application of a hydrostatic pressure

Temperature gradient induced by the contact zone at the center of the aluminum box

Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Pores not nucleated in the centre of the tube

Different pore growth rates and final diameters

Loss of sphericity of large-diameter voids (Gelation)

Observations at the edges of observation window at the end of the experiment

Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Overall influence of T and P consistent with nucleation theory
 ($P_{V_{MMA}}(20^{\circ}\text{C}) = 51.3 \text{ hPa at } 20^{\circ}\text{C}$; $T_{\text{boil}} = 101,3^{\circ}\text{C at } P_{\text{atm}}$)

Average bubble nucleation time for different test conditions
 (at $t=0$ the tube is at room temperature)

Monitoring porosity formation in acrylic resin

Experimental observation of porosity upon resin polymerization

Overall influence of T and P consistent with nucleation theory
 $(P_{V_{MMA}}(20^{\circ}\text{C}) = 51.3 \text{ hPa at } 20^{\circ}\text{C} ; T_{\text{boil}} = 101,3^{\circ}\text{C at } P_{\text{atm}})$

→ But no pore after 500s at $[110^{\circ}\text{C}; 2 \text{ bars}]$ without initiator !

Evidence of polymerization contribution to porosity !

Average bubble nucleation time for different test conditions (at $t=0$ the tube is at room temperature)

Factors affecting pore formation

Polymerization kinetics - A complex Free-radical addition reaction

Power-compensated DSC scan at 110°C

1 - Induction

Peroxide dissociation kinetics

2 - Free-radical polymerization

Active Chain Formation

Propagation

Termination

3 - Trommsdorff effect

4 - Vitrification

when $T_g > T_{cure}$, change to a diffusion controlled reaction
 → Drop in polymerization kinetics

Diversity of heat flow curve shapes

Highly exothermic reaction ($\Delta H_p^{100\%} \approx 450 \text{ J/g}$)

→ Location of Pore nucleation due to exotherm ?

Factors affecting pore formation

Contribution of reaction exotherm to temperature

Effective increase in T within the 3mm diameter tube but limited to 10-15°C

Temperature measured in the tube (0 cm – Center) during polymerization

Factors affecting pore formation

Contribution of reaction exotherm to temperature

Effective increase in T within the 3mm diameter tube but limited to 10-15°C

Location of temperature exotherm peak

Pore location and apparition time

Temperature measured in the tube (0 cm – Center) during polymerization

Most of conditions lead to pores long after the exotherm peak
 → Temperature is not the only key factor

Factors affecting pore formation

Effect of shrinkage

→ The pressure in the resin cannot simply be resolved to hydrostatic pressure

Debonding due to significant chemical shrinkage during the reaction

Factors affecting pore formation

Effect of shrinkage

Debonding due to significant chemical shrinkage during the reaction

Factors affecting pore formation

Measurement of chemical shrinkage using PVT α

+

Peroxide initiators

Very high effective chemical shrinkage during polymerization
 → Local pressure drop at the polymerization front

$CTE_{liq.} = 10^{-3} K^{-1}$

$CTE_{sol.} = 5.10^{-4} K^{-1}$

Porosity formation in acrylic resin

Probable scenario

$$\mu(\alpha, T), \gamma(\alpha, T), \rho(\alpha, T)$$

$$\alpha(T) \leftrightarrow M_w, \chi_v, \rho(\alpha, T)$$

$$\lambda(\alpha, T), C_p(\alpha, T), \rho(\alpha, T), \Delta H_p$$

Densification due to Shrinkage

Limited depression in liquid phase: balanced by resin flow

Porosity formation in acrylic resin

Probable scenario

$$\mu(\alpha, T), \gamma(\alpha, T), \rho(\alpha, T)$$

$$\dot{\alpha}(T) \leftrightarrow M_w, \chi_v, \rho(\alpha, T)$$

$$\lambda(\alpha, T), C_p(\alpha, T), \rho(\alpha, T), \Delta H_p$$

Pore nucleation when depression is effective in the area of resin gelation

- Nucleation is of prime importance, before considering porosity growth
- High Pressure and low temperature limit the nucleation of porosities
- Reaction Exotherm may contribute to nucleation, but with limited effect in the tube configuration
- Chemical shrinkage has a significant role on pore apparition, most likely due to pressure gradients during polymerization

→ Need for an advanced coupled multiphysic model to assess thermodynamical conditions for nucleation

Polymerization kinetics

Semi-empirical model developed taking into account induction phase, Trommsdorff effect and vitrification
(Paper submitted to Polymer Journal – Under review)

Mechanistic model of polymerization kinetics

(Quasi-Stationarity of the species to eliminate (QSSA), Long-Chain Hypothesis (LCH))

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_p \sqrt{\frac{2f \sum_i k_{d,i} [I]_i}{k_t}} (1 - \alpha)$$

Empirical part based on **Richards-type equations**

$$\frac{k_p^2 f}{k_t} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{peaks}} K_{a,i} \frac{K_{b,i} \exp(-K_{b,i}(\alpha - \alpha_{p,i}))}{(1 + B_i \exp(-K_{b,i}(\alpha - \alpha_{p,i})))^{\frac{1+B_i}{B_i}}}$$

Normalization Shape Intensity Peak conversion

Conclusions and future work

Path towards modeling

Polymerization kinetics

Semi-empirical model developed taking into account induction phase, Trommsdorff effect and vitrification
(Paper submitted to *Polymer Journal* – Under review)

Thermo-kinetic coupling

Applied to simulate pultrusion process
→ **F. Zreika, next talk of this thermoplastic session !**
Currently implemented to simulate tube configuration

COMSOL

Pressure due to shrinkage and change in resin mechanical behavior

Soon...

Future work : Investigate the consequences of heterogenous nucleation at the surface of glass fibers.
Analyze growth process of pores in Elium resin.
Application to actual processes for identifying optimal manufacturing conditions

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